

1 What you heard is what you wrote: Dynamic Readings of *ilm* and *adab* narratives in the Islamicate
2 world.
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5 Abstract:

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7 This article explores how the concepts of *ilm* and *adab* (knowledge and exemplary behavior)
8 merged in formative Arabic literature and reached Al-Andalus. Originating in a proto-Sunni cultural
9 milieu, different works were recycled across the Islamic world, giving rise to new literary adaptations
10 and patterns of meaning. With the use of computational analysis, the data has revealed juxtaposed
11 reuse practices. This contribution has found that early Andalusī works initially mirrored Eastern
12 sources, gradually transitioning into a more specialized form of knowledge and performance, based
13 on the legitimization of authority of scholars during the challenging Taifa period.
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27 Keywords: *Ilm*, *adab*, al-Andalus, Stylometry, Formative Arabic literature.
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31 ملخص:

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34 يستكشف هذا المقال كيف اندمج مفهوم العلم والأدب في الأدب العربي الرسمي ووصلا إلى الأندلس. نشأت أعمال مختلفة
35 في بيئة ثقافية سنية أولية، وتم إعادة تدويرها في جميع أنحاء العالم الإسلامي، مما أدى إلى ظهور تعديلات أدبية جديدة
36 وأنماط للمعنى. ومع استخدام التحليل الحسابي، كشفت البيانات عن ممارسات إعادة الاستخدام المتجاورة. وقد وجدت هذه
37 المساهمة أن الأعمال الأندلسية المبكرة كانت تعكس في البداية المصادر الشرقية، وتنتقل تدريجياً إلى شكل أكثر تخصصاً
38 من المعرفة والأداء، استناداً إلى إضفاء الشرعية على سلطة العلماء خلال فترة الطوائف الصعبة.
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علم ، أدب ، الأندلس ، قياس النسب ، الأدب العربي التكويني

Introduction

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3 Early ‘Abbāsīd *kutub al-‘ilm* are “books” of Prophetic tradition that encourage ‘*ilm* (knowledge) and
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5 its intellectual *ṭalab* (pursuit). With traditions often categorized as *ḍa‘īf* (weak), yet popular and
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7 mnemonic, to its listening audience, these *kutub* within *muṣannaḥ* collections of exegetical practice
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9 under the ‘*alā al-abwāb* structure (thematically arranged by chapters) represent the earliest textual
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11 framework of ‘*ilm* (knowledge), notwithstanding the claim that *ḥadīth* collections were compiled
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13 two to three centuries after the death of Prophet Muḥammad. The *muṣannaḥ* material was also
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15 associated with verbs such as *dawwana* and *ṣannaḥa*, which signify “organizing” *ḥadīth*, resulting in
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17 structural divisions and arrangements of aural knowledge and practice.
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24 Section 1 introduces the particular framework of ‘*ilm-ḥadīth* in *muṣannaḥ* collections and
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26 discusses how “knowledge” narratives, while based on *ḥadīth* and its *isnād/matn* structure—i.e.,
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28 chain of transmitters and content—were strongly correlated to *adab*, a polyphonic “genre” and a
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30 powerful thematic engine that is also rooted in another sequential axis, that of the *maḥāsīn* and the
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32 *masāwī* tradition. As a conjoined framework of knowledge and conduct praxis in this early period,
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34 this correlation still enjoys scarce scholarship.
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40 The *Kitāb al-adab*, a book within the *Muṣannaḥ* of Ibn Abī Shayba (d. 235/849), serves as an
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42 early example merging both concepts. Attempts to define ‘*ilm* and *adab* were, however, initially
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44 undertaken by early ‘Abbāsīd *udabā’*. This is evident in state-based attempts conveyed in *adab-sulūk*
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46 material, attributed to figures such as ‘Abd al-Ḥamīd al-Kātib (d. 132/750), Ibn al-Muqaffa’ (ca.
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48 102/720-139/756), and a *mu‘tazilī*-influenced al-Jāḥiẓ (d. 255/868-9). The *muḥadiththūn, udabā’*, and
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50 other former knowledge transmitters—*qurrā’*, *quṣṣāṣ*, *akhbārī* reporters—in their transmissions of
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52 ‘*ilm* were central agents in this proto-sunni environment.
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ʿilm-ḥadīth and *adab*, as concepts, travelled to the West, where Andalusī traditionists created their own Eastern inspired “books” in a still-recent conquered territory with a new Islamic audience eager for exegetical answers for their practice. Eastern “originals” had originated within a developing text-mediated culture, while Western “adaptation” had emerged in the formative stages of Andalusī literature. Examining the structural and textual symmetry of *ʿilm* and *adab* works in this the East-West axis during such formative stages poses a challenge. In this sense, computational analysis can correct our understanding of thematic proximity between works, the “fixedness” or “scatteredness” in terms of structural arrangement or rectify misunderstandings while confirm expected results.

In lieu of understanding the intertextual circulation of *ʿilm-ḥadīth-adab* works from East to West, Section 2 and its subsections, present the results of various methods of cultural data analysis and literary text mining. The *Iqd al-Farīd* of Ibn ʿAbd al-Rabbīhi (d. 328/940), one of the first *adab* works that emerged in Andalus, and the *Jāmi bayān al-ʿilm wa-faḍlihi* of Ibn ʿAbd al-Barr (d. 463/1070), a pioneering systematization of *ʿilm*, serve as core examples of this hybrid literary framework.

The *Jāmiʿ* bears resemblance to the *Kitāb al-adab* of the *Muṣannaf* of Ibn Abī Shayba (d. 235/849), recensed by Baqī b. Makhḥad (d. 276/889)- whereas the *Iqd*, a work inspired by the *ʿUyūn al-Akḥbār* of Ibn Qutayba (d. 276/889), incorporates the *Kitāb al-yaqūt fi l-ʿilm wa-l-adab*. This is one of the earliest andalusī sections that I have found to discuss the correlation between *ʿilm* and *adab*. As of today, there is still a lack of studies dedicated to *Muṣannaf* and its recension and adaptation into al-Andalus, in addition to sources that exhibit the interplay between knowledge and conduct practices in the West.

1 Different “*ilms*” and “*adabs*” in both local and global networks of knowledge were produced
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3 and this contribution aims to provide a first case study on text recycling and theme clustering in
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5 these two frameworks across time and space in the Islamic domain.
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10 1. An approach to *‘Ilm*-Knowledge Data in Formative Islam

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12 If *‘ilm* is translated as “knowledge” in most languages, then it will certainly always be
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14 complex topic of inquiry as cognition an intellectual pursuit finds different meanings and
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16 encompasses everything. Foundational studies (Rosenthal, 1970) underlined that it has been almost
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18 impossible to define *‘ilm*, and most recent ones have suggested that it varies according to the context
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20 where it occurs (Günther 2020, 4). In *ḥadīth* literature, *‘ilm* signifies the concept to understand
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22 Revelation and Prophetic tradition. However, *‘ilm* shows as a cognitive notion beyond *ḥadīth*.
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24 However, “knowledge” emerged as a literary framework in *muṣannaḥ* assembled material and the
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26 *kutub al-‘ilm* were associated and charged with themes, plots and with mnemonic patterns (Samba-
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28 Campos, 2020).
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37 While *ḥadīth* and its study demands a further interdisciplinary approach (Mutaz al-Khatib
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39 2022, 16), it is plausible to say that *muṣannaḥ* collections were perhaps reproduced and read aloud
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41 to a listening, learning audience, eager to comply and aurally understand what exactly entailed
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43 performing religious acts of creed (Davidson 2022). While this is an enquiry that exceeds the aim of
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45 this investigation, *muṣannaḥs*, arranged and conceived by a male-dominated, technocratic elite,
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47 were functioning as primitive aural databases, providing “specific” solutions to “specific” problems.
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53 In early *ḥadīth* literature, the *kutub al-‘ilm* as a literary framework would soon be associated
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55 with popular traditions, showing plots. *Ṭalab al-‘ilm* would be one of its most powerful thematic
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57 clusters. In addition, the vanishing of *‘ilm* and scholars and hence, their *faḍl* (virtue), on *Yawm al-*
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3 *qiyāma*, the kinetic ‘*amal* (action) when teaching and learning with the root twisting of ‘-*m-l* and ‘-*l-*
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m, became powerful mnemonic *topoi* (Eckart, 1965, Noth 1994).

The ‘*ulamā*’ as a newly emerging class, were subject to intense scrutiny by a learning audience. A “scholarly anxiety” in knowledge performance is often exemplified through the collocation of *lā adrī* (I don’t know) or the inquiry *bi-mā adraktu mā adraktu min al-‘ilm?* (By what means have you attained knowledge?). The frequency and usage of these *topoi* -as collocates- can be revealing if quantified, but a quantitative approach may not always suffice to analyze interplay of “genres” or thematic clustering and textual alignment.

As a starting point of view, *ḥadīth* as a textual framework, exhibits a robust and, perhaps, more “fixed” structure. This also holds true for prosopographical and biographical corpora, which can be viewed as early historical attempts at quantitative history (Romanov 2017, 492). This does not imply that *ḥadīth* can only be approached from an *isnād/matn* layer. The development of *ḥadīth* as an exegetical and literary framework was strongly aligned with other concepts and “genres,” such as *adab*.

Adab has been described as a “polyphonic” framework (Behzadi L., Hämeen-Anttila, J. 2015, 70), that was shaped by a “non-secular” but religious dimension, involving practical exegetical ethics and performance, based on the *uswa* model of the Prophet (Alshaar 2022, 32). Further to the correlation between *ḥadīth* and *adab*, both frameworks were built on quotation, displaying a general pattern of text recycling and reuse. In addition, the transmission of Prophetic traditions in *adab* sources provides a broader realm of literary creativity.

Narratives on knowledge and conduct practices originating in the East began to permeate the realms of the Islamic West in the late second/eighth century and early third/ninth century, extending into al-Andalus and potentially reaching the Maghreb. *Ilm-ḥadīth* and *adab* traveled

1 through the Islamicate domain in the post-Miḥna period. This occurred at a time when the *fuqahā'*
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3 *aṣḥāb al-ḥadīth* and *muḥadiththūn* were securing significant philological victories against
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5 unorthodox tendencies. Consequently, a new epistemological significance was attributed to *ʿilm* in
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7 response to the challenges posed by hybrid Islamic cultures and potential *bid'a* (innovation).
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10 The process of reception and transmission of *ʿilm-ḥadīth* also reflects a broader
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12 phenomenon of Islamization occurring in urban centers and outer regions across the Islamicate
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14 world. These works mirrored the interplay and dynamics of text and power that had emerged in the
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16 ʿAbbāsīd period.
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24 1.1. A journey from Kufa to Cordoba

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27 In the Islamic West, the 2nd/8th century witnessed the reception of Malikism, which became
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29 predominant in association with the legitimization of Umayyad power. In the latter half of the
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31 3rd/9th century, during the reign of ʿAbd al-Raḥmān II (r. 206–238/822–852), emphasis was placed
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33 on the promotion of knowledge. The *kuttub al-sitta* were introduced, laying the groundwork for *ʿilm*
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35 *al-ḥadīth* as a scholarly discipline (Fierro 1989, 77). Prosopographical dictionaries reveal the
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37 intellectual pursuit of scholars, exploring centers of learning in other regions of the Islamic domain
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39 and forming social networks.
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48 The first half of the century saw a significant rise in scholars in al-Andalus, evolving into
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50 religious elites. Al-Andalus and the Maghreb became a new audience for the dissemination of *ʿilm*
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52 and the transmission of *ḥadīth*. During this phase, Baqī b. Makhlad and Muḥammad b. Waḍḍāḥ
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54 traveled to the East (Makki, 1963, 33) to collect prophetic traditions. Both studied under Ibn Abī
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56 Shayba, and Baqī aurally recited the *Muṣannaf* in a still *ḥadīth*-reluctant al-Andalus. The *Muṣannaf*
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1 then passed from Ibn al-Bājī (d. 378/988-9) to his son Aḥmad b. ‘Abd Allāh al-Bājī (d. 396/1005) and
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3 to his disciple, Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr.¹ Baqī b. Makhlad who authored a *Musnad-Muṣannaḥ* (Ávila, 1980,
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5 1985), faced accusations of *bid‘a* for introducing the collection alongside the *Risāla* of al-Shāfi‘ī (d.
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7 204/820) but managed to overcome the trial.
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11 Ibn Ḥanbal, Ibn Abī Shayba, and Baqī b. Makhlad form an intriguing ensemble of formative
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13 ḥadīth scholars in politically troubled times. The trials and circumstances of Ibn Ḥanbal during the
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15 Miḥna have been extensively discussed by scholarship and will not be reiterated here. As for Baqī,
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17 he did not adhere to any school and, while participating in trials against *mu‘tazilī* individuals (Makki,
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19 1963, 34), his recension of the *Muṣannaḥ* perhaps had more significant consequences on his persona
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21 than Ibn Abī Shayba’s. The latter gained momentum among traditionists when he was asked to
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23 promote anti-Mu‘tazilī traditions with his brother in the wake of the overturn of the Miḥna
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25 (Melchert 1996, 323).
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33 With the introduction of the *uṣūl al-fiqh* of al-Shāfi‘ī, prospective specialized works emerged,
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35 where a firm correlation between *‘ilm al-ḥadīth* and Malikism rose alongside *‘ilm al-rijāl* literature.
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37 This flourishing moment, as stated by Maribel Fierro, was the “universal in a local context” (Fierro,
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39 2011). However, by the 5th/11th century, significant changes occurred. Córdoba was no longer the
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41 intellectual capital center, as the Taifas (Guichard, 2005) disrupted the previous period of
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43 foundational pillars of political legitimacy and government. How was this cultural and political
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45 environment conveyed in textual sources from a distant reading point of view (Jockers, 2013)?
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53 From the third/ninth century onwards and perhaps due to the fact that the debate on the
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55 written fixation of knowledge had been surpassed, “books” and “collections” increased
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61 ¹ Usāma b. Ibrāhīm’s edition of the *Muṣannaḥ* provides detailed information on the *riwāya*’s and *samā’*’s and the arrangement of the different codex.
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1 exponentially. As power, authority and practices of knowledge unfold, textual arrangements
2 circulate and reshape, becoming also “original” reproductions of texts that possess a structure in
3 themselves. This appears to be the case in the Arabic textual tradition in the Islamicate domain. If
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5 large-scale literary frameworks, aurally transmitted, traveled, computational approaches can help
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7 us understand how formative “genres” were adapted in their recension. These questions and their
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9 answers will be covered in the next section.
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17 2. Dynamic Readings of *‘ilm* and *adab*

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19 This section explores the intertextual circulation of *‘ilm* and *adab* narratives, spanning from the
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21 2nd/8th centuries to the 5th/11th in an East-West axis. The dataset of the corpus, visualizations, and
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23 generated *abwāb*-chapter comparisons have been kindly provided by the project “Knowledge,
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25 Information Technology, and the Arabic Book (KITAB),” P.I, Sarah Bowent Savant.² I also used
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27 Diffviewer, an open access tool designed by KITAB. Needless to say, identifying text reuse using
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29 algorithms that pair up words and phrases irrespective of their meaning is different compared to
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31 manual study (Barber, 2020), which ensures accurate identification, such as synonyms or omitted
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33 words. Text reuse also poses challenges in terms of key words in context (KWIC).
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42 However, this article is interested in the correlation between *‘ilm* and *adab* on a first level of
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44 “large scale” relationship and thematic cluster research and therefore focuses on the usage of
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46 stylometry. For the stylometric analysis, I have used the package “stylo” with Classic Delta Distance
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48 Parameters and 1-gram size for Cluster Analysis. I ran several trials of 100, 300, 500 up to 1000 Most
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50 Frequent Words (MFW), finally settling with a 300 MFS analysis.
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60 ² Percentages of word matches will be provided wherein necessary.
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1 My corpus incorporates traditions on *‘ilm*, *abwāb*, *kutub* of *‘ilm* proper and sections that show pairing
2 of both *‘ilm* and *adab* as “concepts”. I have assembled 40 texts,³ which can be broadly arranged into two major
3 blocks:
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5 A= Eastern ‘ILM + ‘ILM/ADAB sources
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7 B= Western ‘ILM + ‘ILM/ADAB sources⁴
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12 Focusing on the Eastern block, the first reuse cross-overs have shown interesting findings
13 and have confirmed “expected” alignments. The arrangement of *pre-kuttub sitta ‘ilm* sections up to
14 al-Bukhārī (d. 256/870) can be said to be scattered and based on an *abwab*-chapter structure. Self-
15 reuse practices are also common, particularly in certain sections such as “introductions” or opening
16 chunks. Such is the case of the *Jimā‘ al-‘ilm* and the *Kitāb al-Umm* of al-Shāfi‘ī (d. 204/820) (Figure
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31 My analysis is centered on the *Muṣannaḡ* of Ibn Abī Shayba and its alignments with other
32 works of the same period. The latter shows broad proximity with the *Musnad* of Ibn Ḥanbal (d.
33 241/855) (Figure 2), and the *Sunan* of Ibn Māja (d. 273/886), who quoted it almost in its entirety. The
34 reasons behind this alignment are two-fold: contextual and medial. Both are lengthy works and were
35 transmitted in a strongly anti-mu‘tazilī political environment that saw the establishment of textual
36 proto-sunnism. The Miḥna and its contextual imaginary, alongside Ibn Ḥanbal’s case and Ibn Abī
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48 ³ *Dīwān*, ‘Alī b. Abī Ṭālib (d. 40/661); *Gharīb al-Qur’ān*, ‘Abd Allāh b. ‘Abbās (d. 68/687); *Risāla*, ‘Abd al-Hamid al-Kātib (d. 132/750); *Adab al-Kabīr*,
49 Ibn al-Muqaffā‘ (d. 142/759); *Adab al-Saghīr*, Pseudo-Ibn al-Muqaffā‘ (d. 142/759); *Miṣbāḡ al-Sharī‘a*, Ja‘far al-Sādiq (d. 148/865); *Musnad*, Abū Hanīfa
50 (d. 150/867); *Jāmi‘*, Ma‘mar b. Rāshid (d. 153/770); *Muwaḡḡa*, Mālik b. Anas (d. 179/795); *al-Āthār*, Abū Yūsuf Ya‘qūb (d. 182/798); *al-Āthār*, Muḥammad
51 al-Shaybanī (d. 189/805); *Zuhd*, Wakī‘ Ibn Jarrāḡ (d. 197/813); *Jāmi‘ fi ḥadīth* and *Musnad*, Ibn Wahb al-Qurashī (d. 197/813); *Jimā‘ al-‘ilm* and the *Risāla*,
52 al-Shāfi‘ī (d. 204/820); *Muṣannaḡ*, ‘Abd Razzāk al-San‘ānī (d. 211/827); *Kitāb al-‘ilm*, Abū Khaythāma (d. 234/848); *Kitāb al-adab*, Ibn Abī Shayba (d.
53 235/849); *Adab al-Nisā*, Ibn Ḥabīb Qurṭubī (d. 238/852); *Sunan*, ‘Abd Allāh al-Dārimī (d. 255/869); *Mu‘allimīn*, al-Jāḥiẓ (d. 255/869); *Adab al-Mufrad*,
54 al-Bukhārī (d. 256/870); *Kitāb al-‘ilm*, Saḥīḡ, al-Bukhārī (d. 256/870); *Kitāb al-‘ilm*, Saḥīḡ Muslim (d. 261/875); *Sunan*, Ibn Māja (d. 273/887); *Sunan*,
55 Abū Dāwūd al-Sijistānī (d. 275/889); *Kitāb al-‘ilm*, Ibn Qutayba (d. 276/889); *Kitāb al-‘ilm*, Saḥīḡ, al-Tirmidhī (d. 279/892); *Makārim al-Akhlāq*, Ibn Abī
56 al-Dunya (d. 281/894); *Iqd al-Farīd*, Ibn ‘Abd Rabbihi (d. 328/940); *Farḡ ṭalab al-‘ilm*, al-Ājurri (d. 360/970); *Risāla*, Ibn Abī Zayd al-Qayrawānī (d.
57 386/996); *al-Ādāb*, al-Bayhaqī (d. 458/1066); *Adab al-Mujālasa*, Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr (d. 463/1071); *Bahjat*, Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr (d. 463/1071); *Jāmi‘*, ‘Abd al-
58 Barr (d. 463/1071); *Mi‘yār al-‘ilm* and the *Ihyā’* of al-Ghazālī (d. 505/1111). For my *‘Ilm-Adab* Corpus, see bibliography.

59 ⁴ Eastern works show a bigger presence in KITAB in comparison to those coming from the West or al-Andalus. The bio-bibliographical database
60 (HATA/HATOI) provides precise information on names of authors and titles but also on the sources where their textual production is referenced.
61 With regards to ‘ilm, the category *kutub al-‘ilm* was adopted as a classification for books related to this topic and were allocated under ‘Section XV.
62 Otros’. Unidentified works bearing the title of *dawāwīn* (collections, accounts) and *daḡātir* (notebooks) of ‘ilm are also prominent.
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1 Shayba's active role amongst the *fuqahā' aṣḥāb al-ḥadīth* as a transmitter-collector but also as a
2 fabricator⁵ assembling a vast quantity of *ḥadīth* traditions, are political and medial factors that may
3 explain this textual equilibrium.
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9 *ʿilm* narratives usually incorporate sections on the acceptance or rejection of the fixation of
10 *ʿilm* - as *ḥadīth* - through text, though questions on the later arrangement of these sources in this
11 formative period must be raised. The *kutub al-ʿilm*, in fact, can be considered a product of the debate
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17 Also, there were perhaps growing concerns regarding *taḥammul al-ʿilm* - as carrying the knowledge
18 of *ḥadīth*- and the challenges faced in more hybrid and peripheral Islamic societies.
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23 While data brings new sections and arrangements on *ʿilm* -a recent finding has been a *Kitāb*
24 *al-ʿilm* in the *Musnad* of Abū Ḥanīfa (d. 150/867)-, one of the earliest *abwāb* dedicated to *ʿilm* can be
25 found in the *Jāmiʿ* of Maʿmar b. Rāshid (d. 153/770), which was transmitted by his student ʿAbd al-
26 Razzāq al-Ṣanʿānī (d. 211/827). The *Bāb al-ʿilm* and *Bāb kitāb al-ʿilm* are centered on the debate earlier
27 mentioned are thrown inside the *Jāmiʿ* with no order. Ibn Abī Shayba's *Kitāb al-adab* within the
28 *Muṣannaf* includes similar chapters regarding the written fixation of knowledge: *Man rakḥkhaṣa fi*
29 *kitāb al-ʿilm* (Who authorizes writing knowledge) and *Man kāna yakrahu kitāb al-ʿilm* (Who hated
30 writing knowledge).⁶ However, following the *maḥāsīn* and *masāwī* axi, these seem to be put more
31 closely together forming a cluster.
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47 Another author contemporary of Ibn Abī Shayba and Ibn Ḥanbal is Abu Khaythama (d.
48 234/848). The latter's *Kitāb al-ʿilm* has shown alignments with Ibn Abī Shayba's *Muṣannaf*, however,
49 the symmetry shows apparent differences.⁷ The most important one is that Abū Khaythama seems
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59 ⁵ Al-Khaṭīb al-Baghdādī, *Tārīkh*, v. 11, 262.

60 ⁶ *Muṣannaf* (= Cairo Edition), v. 8, 575, report 26939.

61 ⁷ 2,52%.

1 to provide the full *isnād*, unlike Ibn Abī Shayba. This can be seen in a passage (Figure 3) that merges
2
3 two traditions transmitted by the early companions, ‘Abd Allāh and by ‘Umar, respectively:
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5 من يرد الله به خيرا يفقهه في الدين
6

7 For whomsoever Allāh wants good, He gives him understanding in the religion.
8

9
10 ان تكون عالما فكن متعلما فان لم تكن متعلما فاحبهم فان لم تحبهم فلا تبغضهم
11

12 If you seek to be a scholar, be a scholar, and if you cannot, then be a learner [educate yourself]. If
13 you don’t want to educate yourself, then love both of them. If you don’t, do not abhor either.⁸
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16
17 The latter quote shows resemblance to a quote in Ibn Qutayba’s *Kitāb al-‘ilm* of knowledge
18 transmitted by an unknown speaker:
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20
21 كان يقال: إذا أردت أن تكون عالما فاقصد لَفَنَ من العلم، وإذا أردت أن تكون أدبيا فخذ من كل شيء أحسنه⁹
22

23 It used to be said: “If you want to be a scholar, then specialise in one discipline of knowledge; and if
24 you want to be an *adīb*, then take from everything the best of it.”
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28 This last account on *‘ilm* and *adab* takes us to the *‘Uyūn* of Ibn Qutayba. Studying the
29 recycling of the *‘Uyūn* exceeds the goal of this article. This contribution is particularly interested in
30 the fifth book of the *‘Uyūn*, the *Kitāb al-‘ilm*, one of the first books dedicated to *‘ilm* in an *adab*
31 encyclopaedia. The *‘Uyūn* were heavily quoted by al-Jāhīz in the *Bayān wa-Tabayīn* and by Ibn
32 Marwān al-Dīnawarī (d. 333/944) who authored a *Kitāb al-Mujālasa wa-jawāhir al-‘ilm*.¹⁰ All these
33 early examples exhibit that the pairing between knowledge and conduct practices was a literary
34 intent that would extend beyond the East.
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50 As large-scale corpora, the *Muṣannaf* of Ibn Abī Shayba and the *‘Uyūn* of Ibn Qutayba, along with
51 their “books” on *‘ilm* and *adab*, traveled to al-Andalus and were recensed. To what extent formative
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58 8 Abu Khaythama, *Ilm*, OpenITI, 0234AbuKhaythama.Ilm. Shia001903, ms01; Ibn Abi Shayba, *Musannaf*, OpenITI, 0235IbnAbiShayba.Musannaf.
59 JK000786, ms3161. OpenIti, Version 1.6, July, 2022.

60 9 *‘Uyūn*, v. 2, 129.

61 10 9.92% and 5.16%, respectively.
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1 Andalusī “books” on knowledge, social norms, and behavioral practices represented foundational or
2 continuing paradigms regarding their Eastern “originals” demands a closer examination of
3 computational approaches and text reuse. If the recension of the *Muṣannaḥ* changed the *ḥadīth*
4 spectrum for al-Andalus, and even more so if it reached Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr, then how well did the *Jāmi’*
5 echo the collection?
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12 2.1. The *Jāmi’*.

13 The *Jāmi bayān al-‘ilm wa-ḥaḍlihi* of Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr is a critical synthesis of *‘ilm* with nearly 68
14 chapters. As a Mālikī uṣūlī (Fierro 1991, 130), Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr’s work descends from an *isnād* of *‘ilm*
15 pioneers who had made it to the East during a time when al-Andalus and Cordoba had reached full
16 cultural and intellectual growth. However, Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr’s era was markedly different.
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30 In the last quarter of the fourth/tenth century and the first half of the fifth/eleventh century,
31 the Iberian Peninsula was in a state of political dismantling, witnessing the end of the Umayyad
32 caliphate and the beginning of the Taifa period (Guichard 2005). The loss of political and social
33 stability forced Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr to leave Córdoba. The *mulūk al-ṭawā’if* courts were renowned
34 centers of intellectual production, providing a safe space. Next to the king of the Taifa of Badajoz, al-
35 Muḥaffar Ibn al-Aftas (437/1045-456/1063), Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr played an important role. This role helps
36 us understand his production as an *adab* secretariat, conveyed in the *Bahjat al-majālis wa-uns al-*
37 *mujālis* (The joy in literary sessions and entertainment of the audience) and possibly also the *Adab*
38 *al-mujālasa* (Etiquette on literary gatherings).
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54 Looking closely at data findings, while it was “expected” for the *Jāmi* of Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr to
55 quote significant sections of the *Muṣannaḥ* and the *adab* section of Ibn Abī Shayba, it is the *Tamhīd*
56 (a commentary on the *Muwaṭṭa’*) and the *al-Istidhkā*r of Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr that have shown surprising
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alignments with the *Muṣannaf* (Figure 4 and Figure 5).¹¹ The *Jāmi* quotes very little of the *Muṣannaf*.
The *Jāmi* hardly shows any common chapters with the *Kitāb al-adab* (edited by Qahwāji) of Ibn Abī
Shayba.¹² In contrast, the *Jāmi* demonstrates little overlap with the *Kitāb al-adab* (edited by Usāma
b. Ibrāhim) with only 13 common chapters (Figure 6 and Figure 7). Other Andalusī authors such as
Ibn Kharrat al-Ishbīlī (d. 581/1186) and his *Aḥkam Shar‘iyya* or Qāḍī ‘Iyāḍ (d. 544/1149) and his *Ikmal*
Mu‘lim generously cited the *Muṣannaf*.¹³

A closer reading of the *abwāb* also highlights the *Jāmi*’s specificity.¹⁴ Examining collocates,
faḍl al-‘ilm was difficult to find in Eastern sources. This is now differently represented in the West,
as Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr’s *Jāmi* finds three dedicated chapters: “*Tafri‘ abwāb faḍl al-‘ilm wa-ahlihi*,” “*Jāmi*
fi faḍl al-‘ilm,” and “*Dhikr ḥadīth Sakhwān b ‘Assāl fi faḍl al-‘ilm*.” The term *jāmi*’, meaning
“compendium,” appears to constitute a distinct Andalusī ngram, reflecting perhaps a bigger
confidence of Andalusī scholars in their scholarly expertise in this phase.

Another example of Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr’s specialized scholarship is regarding the usage of *riḥla*
(travel) in the *abwāb*. Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr’s *Jāmi* merges *riḥla* and *ṭalab* in the chapter titled *Bāb dhikr*
l-riḥla fi ṭalab al-‘ilm. In contrast, Ibn Abī Shayba and al-Bukhārī dedicated relatively short chapters
to this theme: *Mā jā fi ṭalab al-‘ilm ta‘līmhi* and *Bāb al-riḥla fi l-mas’alat l-nāzila wa-ta‘lim ahlihi*,
respectively. The *Jāmi* of Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr suggests an intent to synthesize, and it becomes apparent
if comparing the three chapters which show only a couple of alignments.

Ṭalab al-‘ilm, understood as knowledge networking (Padillo 2023), associated with *riḥla* and
ḥājj (pilgrimage) extended from al-Andalus to other regions in the Islamicate domain. Biographies

¹¹ 1.11%, 1.74% and 2.03%, respectively.

¹² Al-Qahwaji sustained that the *Kitāb al-adab* could be extracted from a previous collection of akhlāq and adab nabawī.

¹³ 2.24% and 2.01%, respectively.

¹⁴ Examining the *abwāb* of the *Jāmi* in comparison to the selected corpus for this study goes beyond the scope of our investigation. The selected chapters are titled with the most “popular” occurrences related to ‘ilm and adab.

1 indicate that Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr never left al-Andalus (Fierro 2002, 288). This circumstance, however,
2
3 is not uncommon. While the prevailing trend in the Peninsula was to undertake journeys to the East
4
5 in pursuit of knowledge, there were notable figures, such as Ibn Ḥazm (d. 456/1064) and Qāsim b.
6
7 Asbāgh (d. 340/951), who chose not to leave the Peninsula.
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10 Although Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr did not embark on a *riḥla*, its cultural and social imaginaire
11
12 undoubtedly played a significant role in shaping his intention to compile a compendium seeking
13
14 the continuity of authority and textual power in the politically challenging times of the Taifas.
15
16 Moreover, the *Jāmi‘* also reflected the development of a growing social relationship between the
17
18 ‘*ulamā*’ and their audience, scrutinizing the best ways to engage in acts of ‘*ilm*, or knowledge. This
19
20 interplay was initially showcased in an earlier section, the *Kitāb al-yaqūt fī l-‘ilm wa-l-adab* (*The book*
21
22 *of the ruby on knowledge and conduct practices*) in the *Iqd* of Ibn ‘Abd al-Rabbihi.
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31 2.2. The *Kitāb al-yaqūt fī l-‘ilm wa-l-adab*.

32 Foundational studies on Ibn ‘Abd Rabbihi (Pons Boigues, 1898; Jabbūr 1933, García 1972),
33
34 conducted well before the advent of computational methods, already highlighted the textual
35
36 symmetry between the *Iqd* of Ibn ‘Abd al-Rabbihi and the *Uyūn* of Ibn Qutayba. The anticipated
37
38 textual reuse has been confirmed. With the ability to now visualize this connection, it is evident that
39
40 ‘Abd al-Rabbihi incorporated nearly the entire content of the *Uyūn* into his work (Figure 8).¹⁵
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47 The sixth book of this jewel-collection is the *Kitāb al-yaqūt fī l-‘ilm wa-l-adab*, an early andausi
48
49 example that discusses the correlation between ‘*ilm* and *adab*. With over two hundred chapters and
50
51 subsections, looking into the symmetry between the “*Yaqūt*” and the *Kitāb al-‘ilm* of Ibn Qutayba
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53 exceeds the aim of this study, but a quick and easy look, comparing the texts using Diffviewer
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60 ¹⁵ Data shows almost 11.33%.
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1 revealed high textual proximity but also differences in titles of chapters and collocates. A new
2
3 discovery through text reuse and alignments has also shown that Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr extensively
4
5 recycled the *‘Uyūn* in his *Bahjat al-Majālis*.¹⁶
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8 Looking into collocates proper, the previous section argued how western sources incorporated
9
10 the usage of distinctive terms, such as “*jāmi‘*.” Ibn ‘Abd Rabbihi and Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr also share these
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12 patterns. This is the case of the collocate “*jāmi‘ al-ādāb*”, which is the title of a chapter in the *Yaqūt*,
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14 and is also included in the chapter “*Jāmi‘ fi ādāb al-‘ilm wa-ta’līm*” of the *Jāmi‘* of Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr.
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18 Comparing these two chapters has revealed interesting re-adaptations in the East-West axis.
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20 One of these juxtaposed adaptations, is in fact the quote from the *Kitāb al-‘ilm* of Ibn Qutayba, which
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22 was worded by an unknown speaker that was mentioned before in Section 2:
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26 كان يقال: إذا أردت أن تكون عالما فاقصد لفن من العلم، وإذا أردت أن تكون أديبا فخذ من كل شيء أحسنه
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30 In the *Yaqūt* of Ibn ‘Abd Rabbihi, not only does it appear as a shortened variant, but it is now
31
32 quoted by Ibn Qutayba proving the recycling:
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34 قال ابن قتيبة: إذا أردت أن تكون أديبا فتفنن في العلوم¹⁷
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37 Ibn Qutayba said: If you want to be an *adīb* then be specialised in the *‘ulūm*.
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41 Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr, however, seems more aligned to the *Kitāb al-‘ilm* of Ibn Qutayba, as he
42
43 includes the same quote:
44

45 كان يقال: إذا أردت أن تكون عالما فاقصد لفن من العلم، وإذا أردت أن تكون أديبا فخذ من كل شيء أحسنه¹⁸
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49 These variant adaptations point to the formative state of Andalusī literature that recensed
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51 collections like the *‘Uyūn* of Ibn Qutayba almost entirely. With time andalusī works would slowly
52
53 detach from their Eastern originals, having also the capacity to either copy or adapt as convenient.
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59 ¹⁶ 2.62%.

60 ¹⁷ Ibn ‘Abd Rabbihi, v. 2, 261.

61 ¹⁸ Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr, v. 1, 522.
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1 The analysis presented here stems from a close reading examination of *abwab* that does not
2 need computation approaches. However, looking into large-scale works and sources through
3 stylometric analysis has the potential to deepen our understanding of the thematic proximity and
4 clusters. between ‘ilm and adab narratives, spanning from Kufa to Cordoba.
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10 2.3. A Stylometric Analysis of ‘Ilm and Adab narratives, spanning from Kufa to Cordoba.¹⁹

11 The stylometric analysis (Figure 9) of the corpus shows clear and distinct author clustering. Within
12 the Eastern Block sources, a subcluster of early ‘ilm narratives includes the *abwāb* on ‘ilm in the *Jāmi‘*
13 of Ma‘mar b. Rāshid (d. 153/770) and the section *Mā ḡā’a fī ṭalab al-‘ilm* (On the pursuit of
14 knowledge), within the *Muwatta‘* of Mālik b. Anas (d. 179/795). This “book” of knowledge includes
15 only one tradition on Luqmān al-Ḥakīm advising his son. Questions must be raised on the
16 arrangement of this section, as very few ‘ilm books include this tradition. A second work attached
17 in the cluster corresponds to a poem in the *Diwān* of ‘Alī b. Abī Ṭālib (d. 40/661) that exhibits the
18 interplay of ‘ilm and *adab*, showing the paired treatment in a very early context>
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37 ليس الجمال بأثواب تزيننا إن الجمال جمال العلم والأدب

38 Beauty is not found in the clothes that adorn us. Beauty is found in the beauty of knowledge and
39 exemplary behavior
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46 These isolated narratives and sections, alongside the recently discovered *Kitāb al-‘ilm* within
47 the *Musnad* of Abū Ḥanīfa, convey a certain “isolation”, possibly due to the brevity of the *abwāb*.
48 They represent what can be described as a preformative stage of ‘ilm narratives, that slowly develops
49 into a gradual “fixedness” towards the second half of the 2nd century. If examining the structure
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60 ¹⁹ The following section will only analyse a selection of works highlighting thematic clustering.
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1 proper, early *muṣannaf*-type works are paired. For example, the *Āthār* of Abū Yūsuf Ya‘qūb (d.
2 182/798) and Muḥammad al-Shaybanī (d. 189/805), as well as the *Muṣannaf* of ‘Abd Razzāq al-
3 San‘ānī (d. 211/827). The same principle applies to the *Sunan* of ‘Abd Allāh al-Dārimī (d. 255/869)
4 and Ibn Māja (d. 273/887).
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11 Continuing with the analysis of fixedness and structural arrangement, the *Kitāb al-‘ilm* of
12 Abū Khaythama and the *Kitāb al-‘ilm* within the *Saḥīḥ* of al-Bukhārī are clustered together. This can
13 be explained by the fact that Abū Khaythama's work is not a specialized treatise on knowledge but
14 a collection of traditions on *‘ilm* which are incorporated by al-Bukhārī. These works are interestingly
15 paired with the *Makārim al-Akhlāq* of Ibn Abī al-Dunya (d. 281/894), a work centered on *akhlāq*
16 (moral characters) based on the ethos of the Prophet. The correlation between *akhlāq* and *ḥadīth*
17 also serves to highlight the interplay between *‘ilm* and *adab*.
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32 All of these aforementioned works are matched to the *Jāmi‘* of Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr which is
33 included in the subcluster but shows a higher-level divide. Emerging in the fifth/eleventh century,
34 in a period with a more widespread text-mediated culture and after the canonization of Bukhārī's
35 first “book” of *‘ilm*, it is plausible to say that the *Jāmi‘* would have reached a more fixed state. The
36 previous section argued that Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr exhibited minimal correlation and little text recycling
37 with Ibn Abī Shayba and how the *Jāmi‘* represents a specialized work on *‘ilm*, distinguished by the
38 usage of unique terms unlike in Eastern sources and the intention to synthesize.
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52 Early pioneering works on *adab* proper and on the interplay of *‘ilm* and *adab* proper are also
53 paired together, such as the *Risāla* of ‘Abd al-Hamid al-Kātib (d. 132/750), the *Adab al-Kabīr* of Ibn
54 al-Muqaffa‘ (d. 142/759), the *Adab al-Saghīr* of Pseudo-Ibn al-Muqaffa‘ (d. 142/759), and the treatise
55 focused on teachers, *Mu‘allimīn* of al-Jāḥiẓ (d. 255/869).
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1 Looking now into the Western Block, the *Bahjat al-majālis* of Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr and the *Yaqūt*
2 of Ibn ‘Abd Rabbihi are coupled with the *Kitāb al-‘Ilm* of Ibn Qutayba and the *Adab al-Mujālasa* of
3 Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr. Here, *adab*, as a structural framework, seems to be a key factor in the textual
4 symmetry. Other interesting findings correspond to the pairing of the *Adab al-Nisā* of Ibn Ḥabīb
5 Qurṭubī (238/852) and the *Farḍ ṭalab al-‘ilm*, al-Ājurri (360/970), which exceed the aim of this study
6 but open a window for future research.
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17 While the question of whether these sources can be regarded solely as “Oriental” or
18 “Andalusi” is still challenging, within the formative period of Andalusī literature, it is beyond doubt
19 that Western works were mirroring paradigms of Eastern originals. But a first dissemination would
20 led to the creation of works that would show more chapters and a greater thematic sophistication
21 as *adab* has a wider literary capacity than *ḥadīth*.
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35 **3. Conclusions: Knowledge as an experience of sound.**

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37 The correlation between *‘ilm* and *adab*—or expert knowledge in its public performance—
38 is a complex topic that this article has aimed to address looking into the intertextual circulation of
39 the *kutub al-‘ilm* in exegetical *muṣannaḥs* and *adab* material across the Islamicate world. In their
40 *riḥla* into al-Andalus, dynamic readings of “*‘ilm*’s” and “*adab*’s” in both local and global networks of
41 knowledge quest were produced in accordance with different contextual specificities.
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52 Examining the *kutub al-‘ilm* in the Islamic West and the correlation between Eastern and
53 Western sources on “knowledge” contributes to the investigation of the early stages of Andalusī
54 written textual culture. A series of works played a pivotal role in paving the way for stability and the
55 development of specialized works on *ḥadīth*, and consequently, *‘ilm*.
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1 The reception of the *Muṣannaḥ* marked a decisive point in the rise of *‘ilm al-ḥadīth* in al-
2 Andalus. Was Bāqī b. Makhḥad attempting to produce a version of Ibn Abī Shayba’s *Muṣannaḥ*? We
3 do not know, but it is tempting to say that he could have. In this period, early Andalusī works initially
4 mirrored Eastern sources. Such is the case of Ibn ‘Abd Rabbihi and the *‘Uyūn*. But at the turn of the
5 fourth/tenth century, due to the stabilization of text, a stronger islamization and economic and
6 architectural growth of capital cities such as Cordoba, textual recycling took a different turn and
7 independent, authored works emerged.

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20 As al-Andalus entered the Taifas, scholars like Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr, now under political pressure,
21 crafted works in a more specialized form. The concept of *‘ilm* was now more than ever associated
22 with *fiqh*, political power and government. This is evident in the *Jāmi‘* of Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr, which
23 sheds light on how authors and their audiences contributed to the construction of textual authority
24 during this period of instability. The collective *farḍ kifāya* inaugurated by al-Shāfi‘ī could have also
25 contributed to the scholarship of Ibn ‘Abd al-Barr, now invigorated belonging to the *waraththāt al-*
26 *anbiyā’*, Heirs of the Prophet, and the “genetics of greatness” (Ephrat, Hatina 2013, 2).

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40 The criteria for understanding the correlation between knowledge and conduct practices
41 has involved gaining insights into how formative Arabic textual culture was slowly shifting into a
42 Classical period and into the *archive* (Manoff, 2004; Zadeh, 2016). Here, a perception of “book” was
43 key as a growing textualized culture was promoting creed, knowledge and conduct, creating an
44 effect on its audience. If transmitters and authors heard what they wrote, in the fashion of the
45 WYSIWYG (“What you see is what you get”) model, thus, a “textualization of experience” (Majewski,
46 2020) was being produced. Since auralty is deeply rooted in formative Arabic textual culture,
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1 exploring the latter through the lens of sound and its phenomenology becomes crucial for a
2 comprehensive understanding. In essence, knowledge can be viewed as an experience of sound.
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6 However, -on mere speculative grounds- textualized knowledge could have also created
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8 noise (Malaspina 2018, 8). The fear of false attributions and material, weak transmissions of
9 Prophetic traditions but moreover, the necessity to properly act and perform *‘ilm ‘ilm* might have
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11 been the driving forces behind the correlation between *‘ilm* and *adab* as concepts and frameworks
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13 had to join forces. Simply put, as textual material expanded, there was a need to produce works on
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15 what to know and the best way to act on it. This phenomenon was a general pattern in the Islamicate
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17 world.
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31
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35 explaining the structure and applications of the KITAB datasets for this article.
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Appendix.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

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26 **Figure 5**
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Figure 6 and Figure 7

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Figure 8

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